

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Monitoring and Impact Dashboard

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ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Deliverable 8.2

Monitoring and impact dashboard

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Abstract

The deliverable describes the implementation of a monitoring framework and impact dashboard for the OPERAS Research Infrastructure (RI). The dashboard aims to oversee OPERAS activities, measure its long-term impact and give governing bodies and managers an overview to fine-tune the performance. It provides metrics and key performance indicators (KPIs) across various aspects of the OPERAS RI. The framework was developed to provide KPIs aligned with OPERAS' objectives and pillars and to demonstrate its influence on society, economy, innovation and policy. The dashboard encompasses metrics on communication, services, community engagement, financial aspects and socio-economic impact. Impact case studies are proposed to provide narrative insights alongside the metrics.

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Executive Summary

The "Monitoring and Impact Dashboard" presents a strategic framework to collect metrics and enhance the performance and assess the long-term impact of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure (RI).

The primary aim of the Monitoring and Impact Dashboard is to provide a performance overview to the governing assemblies and to help to improve OPERAS' operational efficiency and comprehend the extent of its societal influence. By employing metrics, key performance indicators (KPIs) and impact case studies, the dashboard creates a comprehensive picture of the RI's activities and their repercussions. The rich data collected will empower OPERAS' governing bodies, ESFRI boards and national research ministries to make informed decisions, adapt strategies and understand the RI's influence on society. The Monitoring and Impact Dashboard serves as a valuable tool for managers and decision-makers, offering a streamlined understanding of OPERAS' operations and the effectiveness of its endeavours.

The dashboard is designed as a means to oversee OPERAS' diverse operations across communication, services, community engagement, finance and socio-economic impact. It employs well-defined metrics and KPIs, in alignment with the organisation's pillars and objectives, to facilitate both short-term performance assessment and long-term strategic planning.

To augment quantitative insights, impact case studies provide narrative context and depth. These studies spotlight specific areas where OPERAS' initiatives have led to noteworthy changes, helping to elucidate the broader impact beyond numerical metrics and describe a use case.

The dashboard, hosted on the OPERAS Confluence space, will be regularly updated to reflect operational progress and impact assessments. The main data collection of the previous year will take place in the beginning of the new year, financial data might take a bit longer. The report defines as well responsibilities to collect the data.

A condensed report will be made in alignment with the Annual Report in the first half of the year (first time 2024). Afterwards, the framework will be discussed and this deliverable adopted in August 2024 and again August 2025.

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1. Introduction

Monitoring is a general need to improve the performance and development of an organisation. The dashboard will help OPERAS to oversee its activities in the different fields and as well understand the long-term impact of the Research Infrastructure (RI). It will support the governing assemblies to improve the impact and the performance of OPERAS and will define a procedure to do so. A dashboard for metrics and key performance indicators (KPIs) will allow the OPERAS governing assemblies to steer and control the development of the OPERAS RI. The dashboard builds on a defined collection of metrics, KPIs and use cases in view of overseeing the different activities, results and improvements of the distributed RI. Not only is the list of metrics linked to the different pillars of the RI, but it also specifies the responsible persons in charge of collecting the relevant data for these KPIs at regular intervals. Furthermore, OPERAS members may benefit from service metrics as well, understanding the performance and usage better.

As a starting point, OPERAS has collected key information in the OPERAS Annual Report 2022.¹ Upon closer review, it has been concluded that there is a need to collect more information on different services, the users' community, the communication strategy and the socio-economic impact of OPERAS. This document describes the process of how the metrics and KPIs were defined. We started with a collection of questions to better understand the impact (See Appendix I for a full list of questions). As a next step, a list of metrics was defined and discussed in different boards as well as collection methods and the timeline.

OPERAS will collect its metrics on the OPERAS Confluence space, a web-based corporate wiki. This space will contain tables to collect quantitative data as well as a list of questions that will be answered in a narrative way and provide examples of impact case studies.

The results will be used to improve the performance of the different communication channels and services and address communication and marketing actions more precisely. It will help to define areas, where more actions are needed. We will gain an overview of the developments in a longer timeline. Results will also be published in future Annual Reports. Furthermore, Work Package 8 plans to discuss in 2024 the results and the Annual Report with its members and to learn about the impact OPERAS has on its members. The results will be conducted in an update of the dashboard in August 2024 and August 2025 of the OPERAS-PLUS project.

¹ OPERAS consortium (2023): OPERAS Annual Report 2022. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7928458](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7928458).

2. Strategy and methodology

Defining the monitoring framework is a process to specify which kinds of metrics can be collected and which kinds of metrics are useful to understand the impact of OPERAS and to help improve it. The metrics shall help to define the KPIs. They can show the activity, the outcome and the impact. The aim of this framework is to reach a precise definition of the metrics and gain clarity on how to collect them.

This strategy defines how to develop a monitoring framework for the OPERAS RI and collect information in a dashboard. Collecting and controlling KPIs helps to oversee the development of the RI and to understand its influence on society and its long-term impact.

RIs are designed for research needs, but their impact reaches far beyond science. Funders and governing bodies, as well as various players in the wider economy and society, have become more and more interested in wider impact. It is essential to link the list of KPIs to results that show the impact on society. “Such impacts may occur over different timescales, affect different actors and be relevant at different scales (local, regional, national and EU),”² these pathways and tools were developed in the RI-PATHS project to support RIs.³ Figure 1 describes the pathway of impacts:⁴

Figure 1: Long-term impacts described in RI-PATHS project

The aim is to identify specific activities, their outputs, foreseen outcomes and impacts that are generated along the timeline. The RI-Paths project defines four main areas to collect impact:

² Ri-Paths project, Impact Pathways <https://ri-paths-tool.eu/en>

³ <https://www.efiscentre.eu/projects>

ri-paths-charting-impact-pathways-of-investment-in-research-infrastructures/

⁴ Available at: <https://ri-paths-tool.eu/en/impact-areas>

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1. Impact on human resources
2. Impact on economy and innovation
3. Impact on society
4. Impact on policy

These impact areas will contribute to defining the impact of the OPERAS RI. In addition, an analysis of the socio-economic impact of the RI served as a basis to develop the KPIs. This analysis was carried out in the OPERAS-P project⁵ to prepare for the successful application of the OPERAS RI for the ESFRI-Roadmap 2021 and that defines how OPERAS can create socio-economic impact.⁶

In addition to these methodological guidelines, the OPERAS Strategic Plan 2023 to 2025, which defines the objectives and pillars for the OPERAS RI was used as the basic reference for developing the KPIs. As part of Work Package 2 *OPERAS construction phase framework development* in the OPERAS-PLUS project, the Strategy and Implementation Plan was prepared to achieve the objectives and pillars (Figure 2) of the RI.

Figure 2: OPERAS pillars and objectives

To use pillars, presented in Figure 2, as a basis for the monitoring framework will guarantee that the monitoring process is aligned with the long term goals of the RI. Each objective has been assigned corresponding KPIs and responsible staff.⁷ The frequency of requests for metrics will differ depending on the KPI. For example, communication metrics will be collected at a higher frequency to monitor and adapt the performance on the communication channels. The framework will specify for which countries metrics will be collected. Service performance and usage will be tracked for the core member countries, as well.

The framework will bring together data from the different projects that are linked to the OPERAS RI (COESO, DIAMAS, Craft-OA, PALOMERA etc.)⁸. A lot of data is collected

⁵ OPERAS-P had a duration from July 2019 – June 2021 (24 months) and supported the OPERAS Research Infrastructure by furthering the development of the infrastructure in view of achieving the necessary scientific, technical and community maturity, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871069/results>

⁶ “OPERAS Question 3.7 Socio-economic ex ante impact study”, internal document.

⁷ “OPERAS Strategy – Annual Implementation Plan – 2023–2025”, internal document.

⁸ All projects are listed here: <https://operas-eu.org/projects/>

within the different projects within spreadsheets. For example, the OPERAS-PLUS project works with a spreadsheet to track the different metrics on communication channels and on communication and dissemination activities and selects as well the metrics of the OPERAS services (Table 1 and Table 9).

Table 1: OPERAS-PLUS project KPIs, events and publications tracker

Metrics	Target Year 1	Target Year 2	Target Year 3	Total (IST YEAR)	Total as of today
Website					
unique visitors per month	9600	9600	9600	8525	8525
all visitors per month				11695	11695
The road to FAIR blog					
N° of posts	20	40	60	2	20
N° of authors	5	10	15	2	20
OPERAS Blog					
N° of posts	15	30	30	15	15
unique visitors per month	30000	60000	90000	10015	10015
Newsletter					
N° of send newsletters	3	6	9	0	22
# of subscribers	400	450	500	0	460
Press releases & Policy Briefs					
N° PR produced				0	1
N° Policy briefs produced	1	2	5	0	10
Communication Material					
N° Videos	0	2	3	0	0
N° Flyer and Leaflets	1	2	3	0	10
Social Media					
N° total twitter followers	500	500-	1500	0	31610
N° tweets	500	-	3,000	0	0
N° total of social media followers	500	-	3,000	0	0
Events & Webinars					
OPERAS Conference	0	1	0	0	0
N° Participants in the conference	0	120	120		

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Metrics	Target Year 1	Target Year 2	Target Year 3	Total (IST YEAR)	Total as of today
Assembly of Commons (AoC)	1	2	3		2
N° Participants in the AoC	<50	<100	<150		
General Assembly (GA)	2	4	6		2
N° Participants in the GA	<50	<100	<150		
N° Number of virtual workshops	1	2	3	0	20

Source: OPERAS-PLUS Tracking Sheet

3. Development of KPIs and describing impact for the RI: the Annual Report 2022 and an internal survey

The OPERAS Annual Report 2022 provides a detailed record of the OPERAS RI⁹, such as reports on OPERAS' assemblies, activities, Special Interest Groups and projects within 2022. It provides an overview of the development of the main services and describes the activities to foster the adoption of FAIR principles for data and publications in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) as well as OPERAS' engagement in the European Research Area. Furthermore, the Annual Report describes the measuring process of the OPERAS RI by providing the KPIs and objectives in comparison with 2021. For 2022 a new financial overview was developed (Table 4) as well as an overview of the participation of OPERAS members in EU-funded projects (Table 5). This provides a first impression of the impact OPERAS provides to its members and the national economy. Find more details in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Examples of KPIs in the Annual Report 2022

Measuring the progress of these objectives

Pillars	Objectives	Indicators	Data 2022
Redesigning ecosystem	Putting the book into the Open Science environment	No. of publishers who have joined our network and are willing to enter the Open Science movement	64

⁹ OPERAS consortium (2023): OPERAS Annual Report 2022. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7928458](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7928458)

Empowering community	Adding OPERAS services to the EOSC catalogue of services	No. of services part of the EOSC catalogue of services.	4
	Fostering the adoption of FAIR principles for data and publications in the SSH	No. of members of CO-OPERAS implementation network	64
Supporting biodiversity	Ensuring diversity of open scholarly communication practices through the different services	No of publishers participating in PRISM	13
Fostering quality	Offering quality services	No. of services eligible to Core Trust Seal No. of service candidates for initial Core Trust Seal evaluation	2

Projects, members and services

Projects submitted	<i>No. of projects submitted: OPERAS-PLUS, Palomera, CRAFT-OA, DIAMAS, Skills4EOSC, Grasp-OA and OAEBU; HTTP-OS-NetR was not successful</i>	8
Projects	No. of collaborative projects in which OPERAS RI is a participant or coordinator TRIPLE, COESO, OPERAS-PLUS, DIAMAS, Skills4EOSC, OAeBU, Translation and Open Science project, CO-OPERAS, OPERAS-GER, OPERAS-PL	10
Members	No. of core members of OPERAS <i>CNRS, IBL Pan, Jisc, Max Weber Stiftung, OAPEN, University of Coimbra, University of Turin, University of Zadar, ZRC SAZU</i>	10
	No. ordinary members of OPERAS	42
	No. of supporting members of OPERAS	3
	No. of countries where OPERAS is established	21
Services	No. of services in evaluation	5
	No. of services	7

Source: OPERAS consortium (2023): OPERAS Annual Report 2022. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7928458](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7928458), p. 50.

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As part of the discussion process of a monitoring dashboard a new financial overview was developed for the Annual Report 2022, that includes an overview of the financial income and expenses of the OPERAS AISBL and its composition (Table 4) and brings it in a development of financial equity overview (Table 5).

Table 4: OPERAS overview, Financial statement 2022

Income and Expenses	2022 (€)
Projects incomes	354,862
Membership fees	80,000
Subsidiaries France (ministry and CNRS)	211,291
Other funding	88,953
Total Incomes	735,107
Sub total employee costs	-333,568
Sub total office costs	-51,873
Sub total financial and professional costs	-47,536
Sub total project costs	-126,498
Other expenses crowd funding initiative	-60,000
Total Expenses	-619,475
Projected end of year result	115,632
Financial charges & revenue	-784
Profit end-of-year 2022	114,848
Brought forward end-of-year 2021	59,789
Cumulative profit (equity)	174,637

Source: OPERAS consortium (2023): OPERAS Annual Report 2022. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7928458](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7928458), Appendix p. 60.

Table 5: Financial Equity and project resources

OPERAS AISBL Equity 2020 to 2023

OPERAS project resource used in 2022 and funding claimable

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In 2022 OPERAS has managed 6 projects, of which 5 started in the second semester 2022. 85% of the work- force is accounted for in the project resource.

Projects resource (person months PM)	Used PM in 2022	Total for funding (€)
TRIPLE	15.2	73,200
DIAMAS	1.4	7,442
Skills4EOSC	1.1	5,959
OPERAS-PLUS	5.5	83,217
Translation and Open Science project	7.8	165,237
OAcBU Data Trust	1.3	18,871
Total project resource 2022	32.3	234,295

Source: OPERAS consortium (2023): OPERAS Annual Report 2022. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7928458](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7928458), Appendix p. 61.

Additionally, an overview was generated that shows how OPERAS' members benefit from their cooperation with the RI. The network offers the possibility to develop ideas and to collaborate on applications for European funding. To describe this impact, the Annual Report includes a list of members who participate in the EU projects that also include OPERAS. It shows the impact that a coordinated approach to work on services for the SSH community brings to the OPERAS' members. This shows that OPERAS has a socio-economic impact on the different countries the members are based in, and it enables them to hire staff and invest in the local infrastructure (Table 6).

Table 6: Impact of OPERAS members by participating in coordinated EU-projects 2022

Project	Members	Total Partners	Number of Members	SUM of Funding 2 (€)
DIAMAS	Core members	22	4	35,447
	OPERAS	22	1	32,500
	Ordinary members	22	5	75,419
	Supporting members	22	1	3,819
DIAMAS Total			11	147,185
OPERAS-PLUS	Core members	14	9	154,321
	OPERAS	14	1	122,413

	Ordinary members	14	3	23,418
	Supporting members	14	1	5,167
OPERAS-PLU S Total			14	305,319
Skills4EOSC	Core members	43	2	26,489
	OPERAS	43	1	41,417
	Ordinary members	43	3	42,523
Skills4EOSC Total			6	110,429
TRIPLE	Core members	22	7	541,627
	OPERAS	22	1	76,000
	Ordinary members	22	2	263,832
	Supporting members	22	1	57,821
TRIPLE Total			11	939,280
Grand Total			42	1,502,213

* linear projection of the budget planned in 2022

Source: OPERAS consortium (2023): OPERAS Annual Report 2022. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7928458](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7928458), p. 62.

An small internal survey within Work Package 8 on the impact of being an OPERAS member has shown that OPERAS has an impact on its member institutions primarily in the following areas:

- Network building,
- Strengthening their own position at a national level as an actor in the field of Open Science,
- Increased capacity to receive European funding,
- Increased capacity to invest in open infrastructure and local economic,
- Increased usage and awareness of own services through the link with OPERAS.

This internal survey shall be extended to all members for the next reporting period.

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4. List of metrics and how they are defined

The collected metrics will serve as a basis for defining a list of KPIs that are regularly controlled. Categories will be simple, well-defined, sustainable and reusable.

Communication:

OPERAS collects metrics about the various communication channels and information about communication activities. Metrics are also collected on the various projects OPERAS participates in or coordinates. Once per year, all metrics are analysed in an annual survey.

These communication metrics highlight OPERAS needs, the approaches that need to be strengthened, which messages are already well communicated, as well as which topics raise more interest.

The RI can collect metrics on the different channels, platforms and communication tools. The data is collected from the different platforms and requested through a survey from the different project communication officers each January. The metrics are collected in monthly numbers and are brought into an all-encompassing overview in February for each past year. The dashboard features embedded links to the different collection spreadsheets of the projects OPERAS or its core members coordinate. The metrics categories are defined in Table 7 below:

Tabel 7: Communication Metrics

Topic of metrics	Publications (number of publications of the OPERAS community linked to OPERAS and its activities)	Social Media (OPERAS main communication channels, not from the projects)	Website www.operas-eu.org (Matomo tool)	Blog Operas.hypotheses.org (Matomo tool)
Metrics to count	#number of publications on Zenodo (no deliverables) #most viewed document (in general) #most downloaded document (in general) #all downloads (Zenodo) #all views (Zenodo) #scientific journal articles #peer-reviewed publications #number of deliverables	#Twitter followers #number of Tweets #retweets #likes #engagement rate #LinkedIn followers #LinkedIn posts #reposts #likes #engagement rate #all followers (all channels) #all reposts (all channels)	#visits #visits from most visited countries #unique visits #duration of the visit #pages most visitors come from #most visited pages	#visits #visits from country (most visitors come from) #unique visits #most read blog posts

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		#all likes (all channels)		
Outcome/ Impact	Report on what are the topics OPERAS is most impactful (in terms of most viewed and most downloaded documents)	Be able to show numbers for how OPERAS engage the community via social media	Be able to show the interest from the community at large and to provide insight on what are the pages with biggest attraction, as well as where people are coming from	Be able to show the interest from the community at large and to provide insight on what are the posts/types of posts with biggest attraction, as well as where people are coming from
Topic of metrics	Event participations	Trainings (as defined in the trainings strategy)	Event organisation (can be part of a big event or an external event)	Projects
Metrics to count	#presentations at external events #participation in panel discussions #posters	#number of trainings for services #number of trainings FAIR #number of trainings Open Science #trainings in countries #training materials services	#number of conferences #number of participants #addressed stakeholder groups #number of organised	#participation in consortium meetings (not people attending, only number of meetings) #organised consortium meetings #countries involved

		<p>#training materials FAIR</p> <p>#training materials Open Science</p> <p>#people impacted by the trainings</p>	<p>session/workshops/webinar/ThatCamp</p> <p>#panel</p> <p>#sessions filled (at external events)</p> <p>#number of papers submitted</p> <p>#number of speakers</p> <p>#days of events</p> <p>#co-located events (triggering subcommunities)</p>	
Outcome/Impact	Positioning OPERAS members and representatives as relevant voices in the SSH environment	Empowered Community	Engagement of the Community	Positioning OPERAS members and representatives as relevant voices in the SSH environment, engagement and networking
Topic of metrics (with	Newsletter	Data	Audio visual	

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description)				
Metrics to count	#subscribers #readers #open rate	#downloads of OPERAS datasets #number of data publications	#of views/listeners to each material #number of media publications	
Outcome/Impact	To measure general impact on number of readers and engagement	To measure potential reutilisation of OPERAS community data	To measure interest and engagement from the community on OPERAS-related media	

Services:

A consultation process involving service providers was undertaken via the Services and Technology Board (STB) to decide which metrics to collect to describe the impact and performance of the services. An extra tab in the OPERAS-PLUS KPI Tracking Sheet was created to collect information about the usage of OPERAS services. The service providers supply the information on a monthly basis, which is also the reporting period of a tool used. Some manual collection is required due to limitations in being able to extract historical data from a technical point of view. The results will be brought into a yearly overview in February to be presented in the Annual Report 2023 for the first time. The metrics are collected to provide detailed information about the services and their development and usage. The OPERAS service providers are able to deliver the metrics presented in Table 8 below. The plan is to collect additional information with Matomo and Mixpanel tools to facilitate larger and more automated data sets, charts and graphs such as single sessions, unique visitors, location, length of visits, etc..

Table 8: Services Metrics

Services	GoTriple	Metrics	PRISM	Hypotheses
Metrics to count	# user profiles created # documents # projects # authors # languages supported # data sources # unique visitors (monthly)	# publishers on the platform # books being tracked # metrics per book # widgets installed	# publishers with at least 1 record # titles/works with a PRISM record	# active blogs # unique visitors # active accounts
Topic of metrics	VERA	Pathfinder	OPERAS ID	FitSM Training
Metrics to count	# total projects # total profiles created # visitors	# services listed # registered users # service providers	# registered users # services integrated with # identity providers	# courses # participants # certifications

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		# visitors # searches	integrated	
Topic of metrics	Capacity Hub	Quality	Innovation lab	
Metrics to count	#Institutional Publishers using the Capacity Hub #Number of training offered by Capacity Hub # of diamond journals in the Diamond Discovery Hub database	#Availability/Reliability of the service #Number of Services with a clear defined business model #Personal Certifications	#Number of pilots run through the innovation lab #Number of blog posts on the observatory #Number of innovative outputs (Boost to economic developments/ new markets/ consequences of research) #Increase of Technology Readiness Levels (TBD) #new services added to the catalogue	

The tools and methods to collect the services metrics are described in the Table 9. It does not contain all services listed in Table 8, as some services and monitoring processes are still under development. They will be added in a later update:

Table 9: Details on means of collection

Services	KPI Description	Means of Collection
GoTriple	# of user profiles created	Dashboard/DB
GoTriple	# of documents	Elasticsearch Index
GoTriple	# of projects	Elasticsearch Index
GoTriple	# of authors	Elasticsearch Index
GoTriple	# of languages supported	Manual
GoTriple	# of languages supported for the UI	Manual
GoTriple	# of data sources	SCRE/HMS
GoTriple	# unique visitors (monthly)	Mixpanel
GoTriple	Additional General metrics	Matomo, Mixpanel
Metrics	# of publishers on the	Query the DB

	platform	
Metrics	# of books being tracked	Query the DB
Metrics	# of metrics per book	Query the DB
Metrics	# of widgets installed	TBD - might not be possible
PRISM	# of publishers with at least 1 record	metadata export
PRISM	# of titles/works with a PRISM record	API query
Hypotheses	# of active blogs	Core
Hypotheses	# of unique visitors	Matomo
Hypotheses	# of active accounts	WordPress, but TBD
VERA	# of public projects	Database
VERA	# of total projects	Database
VERA	# of public profiles created	Database
VERA	# of total profiles created	Database
VERA	# of visitors	Matomo
Pathfinder	# of services listed	Database
Pathfinder	# of service providers	Database
Pathfinder	# of visitors	Web analytic tool (GA or Matomo)
Pathfinder	# of searches	Mixpanel
Pathfinder	# of "salient actions" taken by visitors	Mixpanel
Pathfinder	# of registered users	Database
Pathfinder	# of saved searches	Database
OPERAS ID	# of registered users	LDAP Fusion Directory
OPERAS ID	# of services integrated with	Manual
OPERAS ID	# of identity providers integrated	Manual via Homepage
Messaging	# of workspaces	Mattermost System Console
Messaging	# of channels	Mattermost System Console
Messaging	# of active users	Mattermost System Console
Messaging	# of messages	Mattermost System Console
FitSM Training	# of training courses	Google Sheet
FitSM Training	# of training participants	Google Sheet
FitSM Training	# of training certifications	Google Sheet

Community:

The community metrics are collected annually by the community manager. They are provided in an overview in February for the past year. They will help to understand the level of engagement with the OPERAS community, and where to improve. Which numbers exactly are collected is described in Table 10.

Table 10: Community Metrics

Topic of metrics	OPERAS Members	Core Countries/ Nodes	Internal meetings to engage the community	Project Partners
Metrics to count	#number of ordinary members #supporting members #core members #countries of members #publishers in the network (including publishers within OPERAS members associations)	#number of nodes #funded nodes	#Assembly of the Commons (per year) #organisations participating in assembly of commons (per year) #General Assembly #Consortium meeting (all projects organised by OPERAS or its core members)	#number of project partners List of countries from where the project partners are and how many in each
Outcome/Impact	Be able to show the reach of the infrastructure through its organisational composition	Be able to show European representativeness via the nodes	Provide a view of the infrastructure internal engagement	Impact on society as well as socio economic impact

Financial and socio-economic:

The OPERAS AISBL is a non-for-profit Belgium organisation serving as a central hub for the OPERAS distributed infrastructure. It delivers financial information and staff information on a yearly basis prepared annually for the General Assembly in June. The information is verified by an auditor. Therefore, the audited financial part would be available end of April.

Some financial and socio-economic impacts can be delivered for the whole RI on a yearly basis as well as the income of EU-funding and the spent expense for staff and other goods within those projects (Table 11).

Table 11: Financial metrics

Topic of metrics	Financial balance (AISBL per year)	Meeting and event organisation (amount spent per country; this information might be added for later reports)	OPERAS AISBL workforce	Projects income (AISBL and RI)
Metrics to count	#project incomes #membership fees #other funding #office costs #project costs #other expenses	#amount spent per country #additional staff #printing of communication material #technical support #amount for events	#OPERAS AISBL employees #in-kind person per country and per board #new jobs by type (scientific/technical/administrative staff) and wage level	#income per project #income of each member per project #FTE of each member #FTE in countries
Outcome/Impact	Provide a vision of financial stability of the infrastructure	Provide an overview of how OPERAS invests in its community and engagement	Provide a view on OPERAS investment in staff and human skills for the infrastructure	Show how projects are financially relevant

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5. Structure for an Impact Case Study

This section suggests a structure for impact case studies in a narrative form to complement the list of metrics and KPIs. For instance, one of OPERAS' main goals is to empower its members and communities through high-quality training. While the diversity in the number of training activities gives a potential indication of reach, it is equally enriching to observe the impact of training at the level of an organisation. For example, how have the new skills acquired during training sessions contributed to strengthening infrastructure in the long run (e.g., FitSM)? Against the detailed background information about the number of sessions delivered, the number of participants (by gender and country) and of Open Educational Resources (OERs) published, an impact case study will provide insights into how skills and knowledge gained during an OPERAS' training session have potentially led to significant improvements at an organisational level (such as streamlining workflows in view of launching of a new service at an OPERAS partner organisation).

Suggested structure:

- Overview of the set of activities [the OPERAS training] in 2023 (Including visualisations)
- Description of a specific activity [training] and participant demographics
- Significance and reach (what has changed by looking at a case study). Including quotes [from the person who benefitted from the training]

More impact case studies are planned for the Annual Report 2024 on:

- The diversity of OPERAS AISBL staff and RI Assemblies,
- OPERAS as a trusted advisor for national and European Open Science strategies (policy advising + ecosystem),
- Collaborations on a European level,
- Business model of a service as use case

To get a first impression, how those use cases will look like the description of the OPERAS activities and outreach actions in the Annual Report 2021 can deal.¹⁰ There is first given an overview on all external presentations at conference as well as organised engagement events of the OPERAS RI, then a detailed look on the Triple Conference (Figure 2).

¹⁰ OPERAS Consortium. (2022). OPERAS Annual Report 2021. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618693>

Figure 2: Use case TRIPLE Conference

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More examples can be found in the OPERAS Annual Report 2022. In addition, there is a use case on the Crowdfunding Campaign to support Ukrainian editorial staff on Open Access journals (SUES).¹² The whole list of suggested case studies OPERAS will provide are shown as part of the KPI definition in Chapter 6, Table 12.

¹¹ OPERAS Consortium. (2022). OPERAS Annual Report 2021. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618693>, p. 22.

¹² OPERAS consortium (2023): OPERAS Annual Report 2022. <https://zenodo.org/record/7928459>, p. 28 ff.

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6. Key Performance Indicators and Impact

The following Table 12 defines the list of KPIs provided to demonstrate the performance of the OPERAS RI. They are organised to align with the pillars and objectives of the RI. These KPIs are defined for the whole OPERAS RI and include activities organised by core members directly linked with OPERAS. The KPIs serve the governing bodies of the RI to supervise the OPERAS RIs' performance. Some KPIs are defined as case studies where only examples/pilots will be given. This might change over time, if the activities arise more.

Table 12: OPERAS RI KPIs

Pillar	Objective	Area	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
Redesigning Ecosystem	O1. OPERAS as a pan-European, efficient organisation and highly representative of the SSH Open scholarly	Strategic actions	Percentage of performed actions in total (defined in Strategic Implementation Plan) Number of Actions performed	#percentage #number	SG
		Size, Outreach	New members (per country, European and non-European, ordinary)	#Number	Community manager

Pillar	Objective	Area	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
	communication communities	Public awareness	<p>New national nodes/new member countries?</p> <p>Total number of private organisations within OPERAS members</p> <p>Visitors on website</p> <p>Followers on Social media</p> <p>Tweets posts</p> <p>Publications on Zenodo</p> <p>Research Publications</p> <p>People reached and engaged in outreach activities</p> <p>Days of engagement events</p>	<p>#number</p> <p>#number</p> <p>#number</p> <p>#number</p> <p>#number</p> <p>#number</p> <p>#number</p> <p>#number</p> <p>#number</p>	Communication Manager (in cooperation communication leads in the projects)

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Pillar	Objective	Area	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
			Numbers of events (counting training as separate from engagement events)	#number	
		Collaborations/Building a European Network	Highlighting collaboration in a long-term perspective	#qualitative use case	Coordinator partnerships
		Service Providers	Members in the Services and Technologies Board Agreements with Service Providers Financial contribution of OPERAS to sustain the services In-kind contribution of service providers public In-kind contribution of service providers	#number #number #number yearly #number yearly #number yearly	CTO

Pillar	Objective	Area	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
			private Private organisation/SMEs providing service components for OPERAS	#number yearly	
		Financial and Economic	Number of FTE (full-time-equivalent) employees by people (AISBL) place of work/ number of nationalities Number of new jobs by type (scientific/technical/administrative staff) and wage level (AISBL) diversity (examples)	#number #number yearly #number of type case study	CFAO

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Pillar	Objective	Area	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
Supporting bibliodiversity	O2. The Diamond model supported as a major one in the scholarly communication ecosystem (gov & coordination + supporting bibliodiversity)	Community Building Capacity Hub	Institutional publishers using the Capacity Hub Number of training events offered by Capacity Hub Diamond journals in the Diamond Discovery Hub database	#number #number #number	CTO
Empowering Community	O3. OPERAS services published and integrated with EOSC and other marketplaces and communities	Uptake of OPERAS services	Number of users of the different services? Number of Countries in which the services are used Members of the services (Increase of commercial value)	#number by service #number #number yearly	CTO

Pillar	Objective	Area	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
	(regional, national, international)				
Fostering quality	O4. Clear set of well-defined and operational services (portfolio of services + fostering quality)	Services Business models for Services FitSM	#Number of Services #Number of Services in Evaluation #Availability/Reliability of the service #Number of Services with a clear defined business model #Personal Certifications services and the clear-defined business models Quality	#number #number percentage percentage #number Use case Case study	CTO

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Pillar	Objective	Area	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
Empowering community	O5. OPERAS members and communities are trained and knowledgeable in SSH FAIR and Open Science practices (training + empowering community)		<p>Number of training events</p> <p>Training materials available (also as Open Educational Resources made available on Zenodo) (videos, slides/pdf/tutorial)</p> <p>Participants attending training events (with gender bread down)</p> <p>Uptake of FAIR principles</p>	<p>#Number of training days</p> <p>#number</p> <p>#number</p> <p>Use case</p>	Community Manager
Fostering Quality	O6. OPERAS members are trained and knowledgeable in SSH open science service		<p>Number of training events</p> <p>Number of training participants countries</p>	<p>#number</p> <p>#number</p>	Community Manager

Pillar	Objective	Area	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
	delivery				
Redesigning Ecosystem	O7. OPERAS as a trusted advisor for national and European OS strategies (policy advising + ecosystem)	<p>Scientific advisor and engagement with policymakers</p> <p>Engagement with key European initiatives</p>	<p>Examples of consultations (case studies)</p> <p>Policy briefs</p> <p>Notable changes in policy decisions</p> <p>Number of OPERAS publications (research/Zenodo)</p> <p>Boards and task forces of which OPERAS is a member</p>	<p>Case study</p> <p>#number #number of downloads</p> <p>Case study</p> <p>Case study</p> <p>#number Case study</p>	Coordinators (community and partnerships)

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Pillar	Objective	Area	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
Supporting Bibliodiversity	O8. Academic books are included in the Open Science policies	A set of recommendations and resources provided to support institutional strategies and funder policies for open access books	Number of recommendations How recommendations are used	#number case study	Coordinator Community
Empowering Community	O9. Setting up a pan-European OPERAS innovation lab		Number of pilots run through the innovation lab Number of blog posts on the observatory	#number #number	CTO

Pillar	Objective	Area	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
			Number of innovative outputs (Boost to economic developments/new markets/ consequences of research) Increase of Technology Readiness Levels (TBD) new services added to the catalogue new projects pilot	#number #number #number #number Case study	

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7. Monitoring Dashboard and future proceeding

The monitoring dashboard is available as part of the OPERAS Confluence space. It contains a list of metrics and delivers a report per year, the Annual Report, and an internal summary with more details. The dashboard will include the impact case studies to describe the impact of example pilots and will provide case studies on different topics each year. Table 13 describes responsibilities for the different sections of the dashboard and the method to measure.

Table 13: Regular Proceeding

Metrics/Case Studies	Responsible	Time Frame	Results (on the past year)	Method to measure
Communication	Communication Manager	monthly basis	February	Collection sheet/Matomo and Analytics/Survey with Projects
Financial and socio-economic	CFAO	yearly basis	once per year, May latest	Collection sheet, Balance sheet
Services and innovation	CTO	monthly basis	February	Collection sheet, Matomo, Mixpanel
Community and training	Community Manager	yearly basis	February	Collection sheet

As a result of the new dashboard, the first complete report will be written at the start of 2024. The results will run into the Annual Report 2024 but the dashboard will provide more information set in long-time perspective. Through the analysis of the methods to measure impact, it became obvious that the dashboard provides information mainly in the short term. We will gain an overview of the developments in a longer timeline (as much as possible, as not all described metrics data were collected in the past). By collecting the KPIs over several years, the infrastructure will be able to get a long term overview.

After internal discussions and presentations of the dashboard in the different assemblies, the dashboard will be adopted for the update of this deliverable in August

24 and August 25. The metrics and KPIs maybe adapted in practice or changed with the development of the OPERAS RI.

The monitoring is needed to improve the performance of the OPERAS RI in many dimensions and to guarantee the link with the OPERAS strategy. All governing assemblies shall be able to understand the performance and adapt the strategies. It is necessary as well to give an instrument to the governing assemblies, ESFRI boards and national research ministries to understand the impact on society.

Even though it is a complicated add-on to the day-to-day work of the staff and includes the willingness and availability of the national nodes, communication officers, service providers and coordination team in a coordinated approach to provide all this data. The listed metrics are defined for the preparation phase of OPERAS but shall be the base for the monitorin process of the future ERIC in its implementation phase. If the workload is not manageable, the number of metrics will be reduced.

8. List of Abbreviations:

CFAO	Chief Financial and Administrative Officer
CTO	Chief Technology Officer
FitSM	Federated IT Service Management
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OER	Open Educational Resource
OPERAS AISBL	OPEAS non-for-profit organisation serving as central hub for the OPERAS Research Infrastructure
OPERAS RI	Describes whole distributed Research Infrastructure, including the OPERAS AISBL and its projects and core member activities
RI	Research Infrastructure
SG	Secretary General
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities

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9. Appendix I

The following list of questions was collected within Work Package 8 to help understand the impact of the RI and develop a metrics system. These were preliminary questions that opened up a path to help define relevant KPIs. Some questions are linked to the OPERAS objectives, many are taken from the Ri-Path tool.¹³

List of questions:

Public Awareness:

- How big is the audience OPERAS reaches out to?
- Public visibility of the RI: How often is OPERAS mentioned in the press/media?

Communication and dissemination

- What is the number of OPERAS publications?
- How many publications with a Diamond OA model?
- How many people downloaded the publications yearly/per country?
- How many researchers could OPERAS engage?
- How many documents have been submitted to the EC for approval since the beginning of OPERAS?
- How many stakeholders engaged with OPERAS in events?
 - Conferences
 - Workshops
 - Training (objective 06)
- What is the engagement achieved through direct contact, such as in-person training or events?
- How many newsletter recipients? And how often was the newsletter opened/read?
- How often are the OPERAS publications cited and uptaken?

Socio-economic

- Employment in the RI: Number of FTE (full-time-equivalent) employees by age, gender and citizenship at the RI. (Assesses economic impact)
- How many FTE are employed by OPERAS partners in OPERAS-related projects, such as OPERAS-PLUS? (Assesses economic impact)
- Educational and outreach activities: Number of RI staff members engaged in educational & outreach activities. (Assesses impact on Human Relations capacity)

¹³ Available at: <https://ri-paths-tool.eu/en/impact-areas>. Accessed on 31.05.2023.

- Contributions to public policies. Number of meetings with policy-makers and uptake of RI input in committee discussions. (Assesses social impacts/overlaps with Open Science Advisor, Objective 7 below)
- Contribution to Gender balance. (can be applied to e.g., all persons who benefitted from training, to all hired staff in OPERAS-related projects).
- Number of collaborative projects facilitated by OPERAS. (leading to increased collaborations for OPERAS partners)

Increased prestige as a training facility. Number of RI employees who act as trainers.

Community and Collaboration

- How many members does OPERAS have?
- From how many countries?
- From the different stakeholder groups?
- How many members from outside Europe?
- How many are ESFRI countries? In how many countries are national nodes established?
- Number of collaborative projects?
- Number of collaborative project partners?
- With how many ESFRIs and ERICs does OPERAS collaborate?

Services (mainly Objective 04)

- How many innovative services does OPERAS have?
- How many publishers use OPERAS services?
- In which non-OPERAS member countries are users of the services?
- How many people are using OPERAS services to engage in transnational collaboration across Europe?
- How many services has OPERAS published in the EOSC marketplace? How many scientific users use OPERAS services?
- Are the services used in the different core countries? How much did the use grow, and in which countries?
- No. of service candidates for initial Core Trust Seal evaluation?
- Increase in user numbers since the service has been included in the OPERAS catalogue.

Open Science Advisor (Objective 07)

- Uptake of new topics proposed by RI as funding sections?
- Success rate of follow up funding applications at project level?
- Success rate of funding grants from national sources?
- Notable change in funding decisions?

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- Presence of RI in relevant thematic committees?
- How many books are included in Open Science Policies?
- Number of trained trainers?

Economy (mainly Objective 01)

- How many companies use the services?
- How many service providers OPERAS works with?
- How many staff members are hired by the OPERAS AISBL?
- How many staff members are hired by the OPERAS RI?
- How much money does OPERAS invest in local economies?
- No. of publishers who have joined our network and are willing to enter the Open Science movement?
- How many publishers signed the OA Diamond Action Plan?

Innovation (mainly objective 09)

- Setting up the Innovation Lab?
- Published Blog Posts on the Lab?
- Number of proposals submitted?
- Number of proposals funded?
- Number of innovations/outputs?